

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist

Md. Anwar Hossain

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD
entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022
(engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md.
Anwar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a
first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Please visit the Profile of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

12 December 2023

(Md. Anwar Hossain)

Signature

Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Keywords

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md.
Anwar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a
first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Specialized services, specialized payment rate, Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain

Service Statements

Full time Salary of Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is 25000USD/month. A list of specialized services and payment rates of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain has been mentioned in below for the client support in international platform(Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b; Hossain, 2023d).

- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind*. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Process for Client Support & Review

- A written application to Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain through e-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com
- Please send your 'expression of interest (EOI)' to get your specific services from the office of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain
- A payment rate & reply will be generated by the office of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain by the seven working days
- In the EOI letter, a client can also propose the payment rate for a specific service from the office of client

References

- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01. <http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>
- Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8. <https://crimsonpublishers.com/tteft/fulltext/TTEFT.000558.php>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online)*, USA. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>; <https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distilled Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azadirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>
- Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>
- Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>
- Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Engineering of Textile Coloration* City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854575>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11281.40801>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
 Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
 & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
 Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
 Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
 and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
 Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
 Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
 ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
 Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
 Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
 a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
 Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
 City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
 Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
 Chittagong
 Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
 Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
 Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
 Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
 Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
 RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>

Hossain, M. A. (2010d). *Principle of garments production, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh.* Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>

Hossain, M. A. (2010e). *Production monitoring techniques of a knit composite industry.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854541>

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844956>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments* (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28804.50568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311367>

Hossain, M. A. (2015c). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>

Hossain, M. A. (2018). *Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles* (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17899.31521>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311345>

Hossain, M. A. (2019a). *Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article.* *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

Hossain, M. A. (2019b). *Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts.* *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4).
<https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>

Hossain, M. A. (2019c). *Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn.* *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2).
<https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
 Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
 & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
 Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
 Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
 and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
 Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
 Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
 ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
 Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
 Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
 a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
 Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
 City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
 Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
 Chittagong
 Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
 Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
 Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
 Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
 Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
 Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
 RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2020). *My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020* (Academic conference at PhD School, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>)
- Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination* (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>)
- Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95699>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background* (Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>)
- Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286740>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Preprint (Version 2) available at Preprint.Org; Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117436>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics*. <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49095>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24111.10402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208342>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224214>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240342>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>

Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241105>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>;

Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>

Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,
Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

Hossain, M. A. (2023am). *Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.* <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560>; 10.5281/zenodo.8297554

Hossain, M. A. (2023an). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). *Conference Presentation on “Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology”*; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; *Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted.* [http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407;);
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117340>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education” when self-studying of student/researcher is an automatic contribution for national and worldwide development without getting money. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square.* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2831203/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023at). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224012>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind*. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). *Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2024, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10063818>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966475>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933678>,
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933704>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bh). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata].
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10209570>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm* (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Olympia Hotel, Events & Spa Carrer Mestre Serrano, 5, 46120 Alborai, Valencia, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>;
<https://youtu.be/NdPODWoxGQc>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311145>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286771>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10355816>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224211>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252076>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336839>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr.*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cd). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182709>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10209578>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cf). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University,*

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195043>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions. *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia* (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ck). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). UV-Visible-NIR Camouflage Textiles with Natural Plant Based Natural Dyes on Natural Fibre against Woodland Combat Background for Defence Protection. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square, 1-20.* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2126958/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cm). UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cn). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023co). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A., Abser, M. N., & Samanta, A. K. Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent, submitted for publication. .

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
PhD (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science
& Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Consultant (Textile Production, Fashion & Garments, Technical Textiles, Cost
Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Geotextiles,
Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force
and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course
Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court,
Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home
ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber
Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education,
Journal & News), Motivational speaker, literary writer, Certificate courses (Textile & Research)
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College,
Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design
Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange
Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite
Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>
- Md. Anowar Hossain, A. K. S. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Samanta, A. K., Hossain, A., Bagchi, A., & Bhattacharya, K. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, 2(4), 25-34. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 6 July 2022, engr.anowar@yahoo.com